

Odin Telescope Beam Measurements at CESR–Toulouse, 2000 September

Odin Telescope Beam Measurements at CESR–Toulouse 2000 September

Telescope Measuring Facility

Isabelle Ristorcelli, Christophe Marty, Michel Nexon
Centre d'Etudes Spatiale des Rayonnements

Odin Radiometer

Magne Hagström, Magnus Dahlgren, Mathias Fredrixon
Chalmers Institute of Technology

Steve Torchinsky
University of Calgary

Urban Frisk, Gunnar Florin
Swedish Space Corporation

Nicolas Biver
Observatoire de Paris à Meudon

Odin Telescope and Odin Mechanical Structure

Fredrik Sjöberg
Swedish Space Corporation

OSIRIS

Nick Lloyd, Doug Degenstein, Ted Llewellyn
University of Saskatchewan

this draft is by Steve Torchinsky
2000 November 16

Purpose: The main purpose of the series of tests conducted at CESR in September was to verify the co–alignment of the five radiometer beams, and to adjust OSIRIS such that it also looks in the same direction as the radiometer. Note that results for OSIRIS are documented separately by Nick Lloyd and Doug Degenstein in "OSIRIS Beam Alignment Results from Toulouse September 2000".

The measurements were not done in an anechoic environment, so we do not have accurate beam profiles of the radiometer down to the sidelobe levels, however, the main lobe is well measured.

Another goal of the campaign was to measure the difference that is made in the beam profile when the telescope is heated up to a uniform temperature across the main reflector.

Summary: The five channels of the radiometer are all very well co–aligned. OSIRIS is co–aligned with the beam direction of the radiometer.

Heating the telescope did not produce any measurable difference, within the accuracy of the measurement setup.

Test Setup: Figure 1 shows the setup in the clean lab of CESR–Toulouse. The collimator has a paraboloid mirror at the back with a focal length of 15m. It is illuminated by a source at the primary focus which is mounted to the side of the tube on a three cartesian axis computer controlled track. The source is reflected by a flat mirror of 15cm (?) diameter near the exit aperture of the collimator. This mirror truncates the beam, and the diameter of the plane wave which illuminates the primary reflector of Odin is approximately 80cm.

Beam maps are generated by scanning the source in the focal plane of the collimator which results in a plane wave coming out of the collimator aperture at different angles to the tube axis. This simulates a beam arriving at Odin from the far–field from different angles. The computer controls the displacement of the beam, and records the signal intensity measured by the radiometer. To do this, the IF output of the radiometer was passed through a lock–in amplifier synchronised to a chopper sitting in front of the source. For reasons of accessibility, it was the IF input to the AOS which was disconnected, and reconnected to the lock–in amplifier.

Several sources were used to illuminate the collimator. These were the flight–spare Local Oscillator units for the submillimetre channels, and for the 119GHz channel, the source was a phase locked Gunn provided by the Helsinki University of Technology. A mercury lamp was also used which provided a broadband thermal source. The mercury lamp was too weak for the 555GHz channel because of attenuation, and also for the millimetre channel, but it

allowed us to make a direct comparison between the submillimetre beam axis and that of OSIRIS.

For more information about the CESR test setup, see document SSAD51–6, "Report on the characterisation and image quality control of the Odin telescope" by Christophe Marty and Isabelle Ristorcelli, May 5, 1998.

Figure 1: The test setup at CESR–Toulouse. The large blue tube is the collimator. The source is to the left of the collimator near the front aperture. One theodolite can be seen on the tripod between Odin and the collimator just behind Magne. Magne is reconnecting the IF input from the AOS to the lock–in amplifier.

General Procedure: As much as possible, nothing was changed between measurements. When a source was changed, theodolite measurements were made to re–establish the reference axis of the collimator relative to the Odin telescope axis. For measurements with OSIRIS, the collimator tube was lowered in order to illuminate OSIRIS. The OSIRIS beam axis and the radiometer beam axis were then related by the theodolite measurements which ensured that the plane wave from the collimator was always pointing in the same direction from one measurement to the next.

Determination of Beam Centre: The beam plots shown in this document were produced using IDL routines written by Steve. The beam centre is determined by fitting the horizontal and vertical cross–sections of the beam profile to a fundamental Gaussian profile. The program finds the peak

measured point of the beam map, and fits the Gaussian at the cross–section determined by that peak point. The beam centre is taken to be the peaks of the two fitted Gaussian curves.

The measurement control software at CESR uses a more sophisticated method for determining the beam centre. The Bary centre is determined by finding the centroid of the beam profile. This is a 3–dimensional method which will find the best centre estimate even for asymmetric, or non–uniform beam profiles.

In practice, the Odin beams are all nearly perfectly circular, and very close to a Gaussian profile, at least down to the 5dB level. The Bary method and the cross–section method produced results which agree very well. The following sample is a typical example. The beam profile of the 495GHz channel was measured using the spare LO as a source. The two beam centre estimates agree to within 2 arc–seconds. Since the beam width is approximately 2arc minutes, the agreement of the two beam centre estimates is well within acceptable limits. The following four plots (Figures 2–5) show the 495GHz beam profile as a contour map, the two cross sections, and finally a 3d mesh plot.

In the cross–section plots, the solid line is the data, and the dashed line is the best fit Gaussian.

FIGURE 2: od080901: plotted peak level: 38.0000dBm, spacing: 1.00dBm

Plot of od080901

file date: 2008 Sep 0 5h35

Toulouse Beam Tests at 488.6GHz

08-09-2000

this is a 12x12 toulouse map

the centre position determined by CESR bary method is (39161.32, 43703.32)

the CESR/CHALMERS centre estimates differ by (86.8203, 483.719) units

which is (0.3, 1.8) arc seconds

centre is at (2.082,17.106) arc seconds

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.2960arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2938arc mins

ellipticity=0.049

peak=(2.3604, 2.6108) = (39074.5, 43219.6) toulouse units

ref pos=(2.3257, 2.3257) = (38500.0, 38500.0) toulouse units

diff=(0.0347, 0.2851) = (574.5, 4719.6) toulouse units

peak level is 38.3dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 3: od080901: x cross section at y= 2.5372

Plot of od080901

file date: 2008 Sep 0 5h35

Toulouse Beam Tests at 488.6GHz

08-09-2000

this is a 12x12 toulouse map

the centre position determined by CESR bary method is (39161.32, 43703.32)

the CESR/CHALMERS centre estimates differ by (86.8203, 483.719) units

which is (0.3, 1.8) arc seconds

centre is at (2.082,17.106) arc seconds

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.3279arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.3256arc mins

ellipticity=0.049

peak at x= 2.3604arc mins

ref at x= 2.3257arc mins

diff = 0.0347arc mins

peak level is 38.3dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 4: od080901: y cross section at x= 2.5372

Plot of od080901

file date: 2008 Sep 0 5h35

Toulouse Beam Tests at 488.6GHz

08-09-2000

this is a 12x12 toulouse map

the centre position determined by CESR bary method is (39161.32, 43703.32)

the CESR/CHALMERS centre estimates differ by (86.8203, 483.719) units

which is (0.3, 1.8) arc seconds

centre is at (2.082,17.106) arc seconds

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.2641arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2619arc mins

ellipticity=0.049

peak at y= 2.6108arc mins

ref at y= 2.3257arc mins

diff = 0.2851arc mins

peak level is 38.3dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 5: od080901: 3d mesh plot

Plot of od080901

file date: 2008 Sep 0 5h35

Toulouse Beam Tests at 488.6GHz

08-09-2000

this is a 12x12 toulouse map

the centre position determined by CESR bary method is (39161.32, 43703.32)

the CESR/CHALMERS centre estimates differ by (86.8203, 483.719) units

which is (0.3, 1.8) arc seconds

centre is at (2.082,17.106) arc seconds

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.2960arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2938arc mins

ellipticity=0.049

peak=(2.3604, 2.6108)

ref pos=(2.3257, 2.3257)

diff=(0.0347, 0.2851)

peak level is 38.3dBm

no correction for noise level

Local Oscillators Illuminate the Collimator: The first series of tests was done using the corresponding sources for each radiometer channel. That is, the spare LO units and the 119GHz source were used in turn to illuminate the Odin primary reflector. Each beam measurement is presented here as a series of four plots. The first is a contour plot, the second and third are the horizontal and vertical cross sections, and the final one is the 3d mesh view.

The data files for these measurements are the following:

<i>Radiometer frequency channel</i>	<i>CESR data file</i>
119GHz (Figures 6 to 9)	OD050908.lob
495GHz (Figures 10 to 13)	OD050903.lob
549GHz (Figures 14 to 17)	OD050901.lob
555GHz (Figures 18 to 21)	OD050902.lob
572GHz (Figures 22 to 25)	OD0409_2.lob

Table 1: data files for test series 1

Figure 26 is a plot of the relative beam positions of all five beams. For comparison, Figure 27 shows the same measurement which was done at Chalmers in October 1999. The Chalmers measurement was done directly from the radiometer beam. That is, the Odin telescope is not included in the measurements shown in Figure 27.

Measured beam parameters are summarised in Table 2 below. Note that the beam position is referenced to the centre of the CESR map which is not an indication of the telescope beam offset! Also note that the beam radius for 119GHz is bigger than expected which is due to the illumination of the collimator by the corrugated feedhorn of the 119GHz Gunn source, which results in a non-flat wave-front coming from the collimator aperture. For a correct estimate of the beam width, one must deconvolve the beams of the Odin telescope and the combination of the collimator and corrugated horn. Tests in 1998 using the Helsinki University of Technology hologram showed that the 119GHz beam size was 4.7 arc minutes, very close to the expected value.

Odin Telescope Beam Measurements at CESR–Toulouse, 2000 September

<i>Radiometer frequency channel</i>	<i>Beam centre (x) arc–mins</i>	<i>Beam centre (y) arc–mins</i>	<i>3dB radius (x) arc–mins</i>	<i>3dB radius (y) arc–mins</i>
119GHz	0.203	0.070	6.300	6.370
495GHz	0.034	–0.014	1.280	1.272
549GHz	0.097	0.082	1.093	1.073
555GHz	0.019	0.034	1.037	1.091
572GHz	–0.023	–0.010	1.024	1.063

Table 2: beam positions and widths measured using LO source

FIGURE 6: od050908: plotted peak level: 38.0000dBm, spacing: 1.00dBm

x (arc mins)
Plot of od050908
file date: 2006 Sep 0 2h40
2000 Sept 6
Toulouse Beam Tests at 119GHz
No correction for corrugated horn

Fit at 3.0dB
W3dB= 6.3390arc mins
W 3.0dB= 6.3281arc mins
ellipticity=0.010
peak=(10.4723, 10.3397) = (173358.7, 171162.7) toulouse units
ref pos=(10.2694, 10.2694) = (170000.0, 170000.0) toulouse units
diff=(0.2029, 0.0702) = (3358.7, 1162.7) toulouse units
peak level is 38.5dBm
no correction for noise level

FIGURE 7: od050908: x cross section at y= 10.8735

Plot of od050908
file date: 2006 Sep 0 2h40
2000 Sept 6
Toulouse Beam Tests at 119GHz
No correction for corrugated horn

Fit at 3.0dB
W3dB= 6.3063arc mins
W 3.0dB= 6.2955arc mins
ellipticity=0.010
peak at x= 10.4723arc mins
ref at x= 10.2694arc mins
diff = 0.2029arc mins
peak level is 38.5dBm
no correction for noise level

FIGURE 8: od050908: y cross section at x= 10.8735

Plot of od050908

file date: 2006 Sep 0 2h40

2000 Sept 6

Toulouse Beam Tests at 119GHz

No correction for corrugated horn

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 6.3716arc mins

W 3.0dB= 6.3607arc mins

ellipticity=0.010

peak at y= 10.3397arc mins

ref at y= 10.2694arc mins

diff = 0.0702arc mins

peak level is 38.5dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 9: od050908: 3d mesh plot

Plot of od050908

file date: 2006 Sep 0 2h40

2000 Sept 6

Toulouse Beam Tests at 119GHz

No correction for corrugated horn

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 6.3390arc mins

W 3.0dB= 6.3281arc mins

ellipticity=0.010

peak=(10.4723, 10.3397)

ref pos=(10.2694, 10.2694)

diff=(0.2029, 0.0702)

peak level is 38.5dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 10: od050903: plotted peak level: 37.0000dBm, spacing: 1.00dBm

Plot of od050903

file date: 2006 Sep 0 2h39

2000 Sept 4

Toulouse Beam Tests at 495GHz

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.2749arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2727arc mins

ellipticity=0.005

peak=(2.3597, 2.3112) = (39063.0, 38260.4) toulouse units

ref pos=(2.3257, 2.3257) = (38500.0, 38500.0) toulouse units

diff=(0.0340, -0.0145) = (563.0, -239.6) toulouse units

peak level is 37.5dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 11: od050903: x cross section at y= 2.1143

Plot of od050903

file date: 2006 Sep 0 2h39

2000 Sept 4

Toulouse Beam Tests at 495GHz

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.2781arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2759arc mins

ellipticity=0.005

peak at x= 2.3597arc mins

ref at x= 2.3257arc mins

diff = 0.0340arc mins

peak level is 37.5dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 12: od050903: y cross section at x= 2.5372

Plot of od050903

file date: 2006 Sep 0 2h39

2000 Sept 4

Toulouse Beam Tests at 495GHz

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.2717arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2695arc mins

ellipticity=0.005

peak at y= 2.3112arc mins

ref at y= 2.3257arc mins

diff = -0.0145arc mins

peak level is 37.5dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 13: od050903: 3d mesh plot

Plot of od050903

file date: 2006 Sep 0 2h39

2000 Sept 4

Toulouse Beam Tests at 495GHz

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.2749arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2727arc mins

ellipticity=0.005

peak=(2.3597, 2.3112)

ref pos=(2.3257, 2.3257)

diff=(0.0340, -0.0145)

peak level is 37.5dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 14: od050901: plotted peak level: 38.0000dBm, spacing: 1.00dBm

Plot of od050901

file date: 2005 Sep 0 4h00

2000 September 5

Toulouse Beam Tests at 547.7GHz

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.0829arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0811arc mins

ellipticity=0.018

peak=(2.4224, 2.4074) = (40100.9, 39851.8) toulouse units

ref pos=(2.3257, 2.3257) = (38500.0, 38500.0) toulouse units

diff=(0.0967, 0.0817) = (1600.9, 1351.8) toulouse units

peak level is 39.0dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 15: od050901: x cross section at y= 2.5372

x (arc mins)
Plot of od050901
file date: 2005 Sep 0 4h00
2000 September 5
Toulouse Beam Tests at 547.7GHz
Fit at 3.0dB
W3dB= 1.0926arc mins
W 3.0dB= 1.0908arc mins
ellipticity=0.018
peak at x= 2.4224arc mins
ref at x= 2.3257arc mins
diff = 0.0967arc mins
peak level is 39.0dBm
no correction for noise level

FIGURE 16: od050901: y cross section at x= 2.5372

Plot of od050901

file date: 2005 Sep 0 4h00

2000 September 5

Toulouse Beam Tests at 547.7GHz

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.0733arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0714arc mins

ellipticity=0.018

peak at y= 2.4074arc mins

ref at y= 2.3257arc mins

diff = 0.0817arc mins

peak level is 39.0dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 17: od050901: 3d mesh plot

Plot of od050901

file date: 2005 Sep 0 4h00

2000 September 5

Toulouse Beam Tests at 547.7GHz

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.0829arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0811arc mins

ellipticity=0.018

peak=(2.4224, 2.4074)

ref pos=(2.3257, 2.3257)

diff=(0.0967, 0.0817)

peak level is 39.0dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 18: od050902: plotted peak level: 37.0000dBm, spacing: 1.00dBm

Plot of od050902

file date: 2006 Sep 0 2h39

2000 Sept 5

Toulouse Beam Tests at 555GHz

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.0644arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0626arc mins

ellipticity=0.051

peak=(2.3443, 2.3598) = (38807.0, 39063.4) toulouse units

ref pos=(2.3257, 2.3257) = (38500.0, 38500.0) toulouse units

diff=(0.0185, 0.0340) = (307.0, 563.4) toulouse units

peak level is 37.3dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 19: od050902: x cross section at y= 2.5372

Plot of od050902
file date: 2006 Sep 0 2h39
2000 Sept 5
Toulouse Beam Tests at 555GHz
Fit at 3.0dB
W3dB= 1.0374arc mins
W 3.0dB= 1.0356arc mins
ellipticity=0.051
peak at x= 2.3443arc mins
ref at x= 2.3257arc mins
diff = 0.0185arc mins
peak level is 37.3dBm
no correction for noise level

FIGURE 20: od050902: y cross section at x= 2.5372

Plot of od050902

file date: 2006 Sep 0 2h39

2000 Sept 5

Toulouse Beam Tests at 555GHz

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.0914arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0895arc mins

ellipticity=0.051

peak at y= 2.3598arc mins

ref at y= 2.3257arc mins

diff = 0.0340arc mins

peak level is 37.3dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 21: od050902: 3d mesh plot

Plot of od050902

file date: 2006 Sep 0 2h39

2000 Sept 5

Toulouse Beam Tests at 555GHz

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.0644arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0626arc mins

ellipticity=0.051

peak=(2.3443, 2.3598)

ref pos=(2.3257, 2.3257)

diff=(0.0185, 0.0340)

peak level is 37.3dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 22: od0409_2: plotted peak level: 34.0000dBm, spacing: 1.00dBm

Plot of od0409_2

file date: 2006 Sep 0 3h01

2000 Sept 4

Toulouse Beam Tests at 572.5GHz

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.0443arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0425arc mins

ellipticity=0.039

peak=(2.3026, 2.3161) = (38117.7, 38340.3) toulouse units

ref pos=(2.3257, 2.3257) = (38500.0, 38500.0) toulouse units

diff=(-0.0231, -0.0096) = (-382.3, -159.7) toulouse units

peak level is 34.3dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 23: od0409_2: x cross section at y= 2.1143

Plot of od0409_2
file date: 2006 Sep 0 3h01
2000 Sept 4
Toulouse Beam Tests at 572.5GHz

Fit at 3.0dB
W3dB= 1.0237arc mins
W 3.0dB= 1.0219arc mins
ellipticity=0.039
peak at x= 2.3026arc mins
ref at x= 2.3257arc mins
diff = -0.0231arc mins
peak level is 34.3dBm
no correction for noise level

FIGURE 24: od0409_2: y cross section at x= 2.5372

Plot of od0409_2

file date: 2006 Sep 0 3h01

2000 Sept 4

Toulouse Beam Tests at 572.5GHz

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.0648arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0630arc mins

ellipticity=0.039

peak at y= 2.3161arc mins

ref at y= 2.3257arc mins

diff = -0.0096arc mins

peak level is 34.3dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 25: od0409_2: 3d mesh plot

Plot of od0409_2

file date: 2006 Sep 0 3h01

2000 Sept 4

Toulouse Beam Tests at 572.5GHz

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.0443arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0425arc mins

ellipticity=0.039

peak=(2.3026, 2.3161)

ref pos=(2.3257, 2.3257)

diff=(-0.0231, -0.0096)

peak level is 34.3dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 26:
Beam alignment measurements
at CESR Toulouse
LD source

- 572GHz: DD0409_2.LOB
- 555GHz: DD050902.LOB
- 549GHz: DD050901.LOB
- 495GHz: DD050903.LOB
- 119GHz: DD050908.LOB

1/10 FWHM beam
at 119GHz

FIGURE 27: Chalmers Measurement
of Radiometer beams co-alignment
at the focal plane

nominal
beam
centre

1/10 FWHM
beam
diameter
for submm
beams

Mercury Lamp Illuminates the Collimator: The next series of tests were done using the mercury lamp to illuminate the collimator. The idea was to use a common source for all channels. This would have the benefit of having a consistent setup between measurements. It would be possible to go from one channel to the next without physically disturbing the setup.

It didn't quite work out that way. Tests were done in two series. In between, the aperture in front of the mercury lamp was removed in order to make an attempt at 119GHz. Afterwards, the stop down aperture was replaced, but with a slight offset compared to the previous position. This offset was determined by comparing measurements at 495GHz before and after the attempt at 119GHz.

The 119GHz channel was not able to detect the signal from the mercury lamp which was insufficiently bright at that frequency. For the 555GHz channel, there was too much attenuation of the signal due to water in the air.

Figure 48 shows the relative co–alignment of the three submillimetre channels 495GHz, 549GHz, and 572GHz using the mercury lamp to illuminate the collimator

<i>Radiometer frequency channel</i>	<i>CESR data file</i>
495GHz (Figures 28 to 39)	OD060905.lob OD060908.lob OD060907.lob
549GHz (Figures 40 to 43)	OD060906.lob
572GHz (Figures 44 to 47)	OD060903.lob

Table 3: data files for the tests using the mercury lamp

The entire series of measurements using the mercury lamp was repeated. The data files are listed in Table 4, and Figure 61 shows the relative co–alignment of the three submillimetre channels 495GHz, 549GHz, and 572GHz.

<i>Radiometer frequency channel</i>	<i>CESR data file</i>
495GHz (Figures 49 to 52)	OD080903.lob
549GHz (Figures 53 to 56)	OD080905.lob
572GHz (Figures 57 to 60)	OD080904.lob

Table 4: data files for the tests with the mercury lamp, second series.

FIGURE 28: od060905: plotted peak level: 37.0000dBm, spacing: 1.00dBm

Plot of od060905

file date: 2006 Sep 0 7h49

2000 Sept 6

Toulouse Beam Tests at 488.6GHz

with the mercury lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.2523arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2501arc mins

ellipticity=0.040

peak=(2.3991, 2.7881) = (39714.0, 46154.3) toulouse units

ref pos=(2.7486, 2.7486) = (45500.0, 45500.0) toulouse units

diff=(-0.3495, 0.0395) = (-5786.0, 654.3) toulouse units

peak level is 37.6dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 29: od060905: x cross section at y= 2.9600

Plot of od060905
file date: 2006 Sep 0 7h49
2000 Sept 6
Toulouse Beam Tests at 488.6GHz
with the mercury lamp
Fit at 3.0dB
W3dB= 1.2776arc mins
W 3.0dB= 1.2754arc mins
ellipticity=0.040
peak at x= 2.3991arc mins
ref at x= 2.7486arc mins
diff = -0.3495arc mins
peak level is 37.5dBm
no correction for noise level

FIGURE 30: od060905: y cross section at x= 2.5372

Plot of od060905
file date: 2006 Sep 0 7h49
2000 Sept 6
Toulouse Beam Tests at 488.6GHz
with the mercury lamp
Fit at 3.0dB
W3dB= 1.2270arc mins
W 3.0dB= 1.2248arc mins
ellipticity=0.040
peak at y= 2.7881arc mins
ref at y= 2.7486arc mins
diff = 0.0395arc mins
peak level is 37.7dBm
no correction for noise level

FIGURE 31: od060905: 3d mesh plot

Plot of od060905

file date: 2006 Sep 0 7h49

2000 Sept 6

Toulouse Beam Tests at 488.6GHz

with the mercury lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.2523arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2501arc mins

ellipticity=0.040

peak=(2.3991, 2.7881)

ref pos=(2.7486, 2.7486)

diff=(-0.3495, 0.0395)

peak level is 37.6dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 32: od060908: plotted peak level: 37.0000dBm, spacing: 1.00dBm

Plot of od060908

file date: 2006 Sep 0 9h52

2000 Sept 6

Toulouse Beam Tests at 488.6GHz

with the mercury lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.2588arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2566arc mins

ellipticity=0.038

peak=(2.4412, 2.7429) = (40411.9, 45405.3) toulouse units

ref pos=(2.7486, 2.7486) = (45500.0, 45500.0) toulouse units

diff=(-0.3074, -0.0057) = (-5088.0, -94.6) toulouse units

peak level is 37.3dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 33: od060908: x cross section at y= 2.5372

Plot of od060908
file date: 2006 Sep 0 9h52
2000 Sept 6
Toulouse Beam Tests at 488.6GHz
with the mercury lamp
Fit at 3.0dB
W3dB= 1.2825arc mins
W 3.0dB= 1.2803arc mins
ellipticity=0.038
peak at x= 2.4412arc mins
ref at x= 2.7486arc mins
diff = -0.3074arc mins
peak level is 37.2dBm
no correction for noise level

FIGURE 34: od060908: y cross section at x= 2.5372

Plot of od060908

file date: 2006 Sep 0 9h52

2000 Sept 6

Toulouse Beam Tests at 488.6GHz

with the mercury lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.2351arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2330arc mins

ellipticity=0.038

peak at y= 2.7429arc mins

ref at y= 2.7486arc mins

diff = -0.0057arc mins

peak level is 37.3dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 35: od060908: 3d mesh plot

Plot of od060908

file date: 2006 Sep 0 9h52

2000 Sept 6

Toulouse Beam Tests at 488.6GHz

with the mercury lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.2588arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2566arc mins

ellipticity=0.038

peak=(2.4412, 2.7429)

ref pos=(2.7486, 2.7486)

diff=(-0.3074, -0.0057)

peak level is 37.3dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 36: od060907: plotted peak level: 37.0000dBm, spacing: 1.00dBm

Plot of od060907

file date: 2006 Sep 0 9h51

2000 Sept 6

Toulouse Beam Tests at 488.6GHz

with the mercury lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.2681arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2659arc mins

ellipticity=0.041

peak=(1.9889, 2.3077) = (32924.0, 38202.5) toulouse units

ref pos=(2.3257, 2.3257) = (38500.0, 38500.0) toulouse units

diff=(-0.3368, -0.0180) = (-5576.0, -297.5) toulouse units

peak level is 37.3dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 37: od060907: x cross section at y= 2.1143

Plot of od060907

file date: 2006 Sep 0 9h51

2000 Sept 6

Toulouse Beam Tests at 488.6GHz

with the mercury lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.2941arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2918arc mins

ellipticity=0.041

peak at x= 1.9889arc mins

ref at x= 2.3257arc mins

diff = -0.3368arc mins

peak level is 37.2dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 38: od060907: y cross section at x= 2.1143

Plot of od060907

file date: 2006 Sep 0 9h51

2000 Sept 6

Toulouse Beam Tests at 488.6GHz

with the mercury lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.2422arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2400arc mins

ellipticity=0.041

peak at y= 2.3077arc mins

ref at y= 2.3257arc mins

diff = -0.0180arc mins

peak level is 37.3dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 39: od060907: 3d mesh plot

Plot of od060907

file date: 2006 Sep 0 9h51

2000 Sept 6

Toulouse Beam Tests at 488.6GHz

with the mercury lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.2681arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2659arc mins

ellipticity=0.041

peak=(1.9889, 2.3077)

ref pos=(2.3257, 2.3257)

diff=(-0.3368, -0.0180)

peak level is 37.3dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 40: od060906: plotted peak level: 35.0000dBm, spacing: 1.00dBm

Plot of od060906

file date: 2006 Sep 0 9h51

2000 Sept 6

Toulouse Beam Tests at 541.06GHz

with the mercury lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.2439arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2417arc mins

ellipticity=0.048

peak=(2.5563, 2.7831) = (42317.1, 46072.2) toulouse units

ref pos=(2.7486, 2.7486) = (45500.0, 45500.0) toulouse units

diff=(-0.1923, 0.0346) = (-3182.9, 572.2) toulouse units

peak level is 35.7dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 41: od060906: x cross section at y= 2.9600

Plot of od060906

file date: 2006 Sep 0 9h51

2000 Sept 6

Toulouse Beam Tests at 541.06GHz

with the mercury lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.2141arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2120arc mins

ellipticity=0.048

peak at x= 2.5563arc mins

ref at x= 2.7486arc mins

diff = -0.1923arc mins

peak level is 35.8dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 42: od060906: y cross section at x= 2.5372

Plot of od060906
file date: 2006 Sep 0 9h51
2000 Sept 6
Toulouse Beam Tests at 541.06GHz
with the mercury lamp
Fit at 3.0dB
W3dB= 1.2736arc mins
W 3.0dB= 1.2715arc mins
ellipticity=0.048
peak at y= 2.7831arc mins
ref at y= 2.7486arc mins
diff = 0.0346arc mins
peak level is 35.7dBm
no correction for noise level

FIGURE 43: od060906: 3d mesh plot

Plot of od060906

file date: 2006 Sep 0 9h51

2000 Sept 6

Toulouse Beam Tests at 541.06GHz

with the mercury lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.2439arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2417arc mins

ellipticity=0.048

peak=(2.5563, 2.7831)

ref pos=(2.7486, 2.7486)

diff=(-0.1923, 0.0346)

peak level is 35.7dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 44: od060903: plotted peak level: 38.0000dBm, spacing: 1.00dBm

Plot of od060903

file date: 2006 Sep 0 7h49

2000 Sept 6

Toulouse Beam Tests at 572GHz

with the mercury lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.1548arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.1529arc mins

ellipticity=0.048

peak=(2.2164, 2.2375) = (36691.1, 37039.7) toulouse units

ref pos=(2.3257, 2.3257) = (38500.0, 38500.0) toulouse units

diff=(-0.1093, -0.0882) = (-1808.9, -1460.3) toulouse units

peak level is 38.2dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 45: od060903: x cross section at y= 2.1143

Plot of od060903

file date: 2006 Sep 0 7h49

2000 Sept 6

Toulouse Beam Tests at 572GHz

with the mercury lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.1823arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.1803arc mins

ellipticity=0.048

peak at x= 2.2164arc mins

ref at x= 2.3257arc mins

diff = -0.1093arc mins

peak level is 38.1dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 46: od060903: y cross section at x= 2.1143

Plot of od060903

file date: 2006 Sep 0 7h49

2000 Sept 6

Toulouse Beam Tests at 572GHz

with the mercury lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.1274arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.1254arc mins

ellipticity=0.048

peak at y= 2.2375arc mins

ref at y= 2.3257arc mins

diff = -0.0882arc mins

peak level is 38.2dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 47: od060903: 3d mesh plot

Plot of od060903

file date: 2006 Sep 0 7h49

2000 Sept 6

Toulouse Beam Tests at 572GHz

with the mercury lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.1548arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.1529arc mins

ellipticity=0.048

peak=(2.2164, 2.2375)

ref pos=(2.3257, 2.3257)

diff=(-0.1093, -0.0882)

peak level is 38.2dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 48: Toulouse Beam Alignment Measurements using the Mercury Lamp

positions taken from:

572GHz: 0D060903.L0B

549GHz: 0D060906.L0B

495GHz: 0D060905.L0B, 0D060908.L0B and 0D060907.L0B

The first two were used to relate the position change that occurred when the source was removed and replaced for the attempt at 119GHz. The position shift from before to after was $\langle 0.0421, -0.0453 \rangle$.

0D060907.L0B was used as a comparison to 0D060908.L0B to verify the repeatability of the setup. The precision is determined to be ± 0.03 .

FIGURE 49: od080903: plotted peak level: 37.0000dBm, spacing: 1.00dBm

Plot of od080903

file date: 2008 Sep 0 14h09

Toulouse Beam Tests at 488.6GHz

2000 September 8

Mercury Lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.2659arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2637arc mins

ellipticity=0.054

peak=(2.3573, 2.2388) = (39023.4, 37060.4) toulouse units

ref pos=(2.3257, 2.3257) = (38500.0, 38500.0) toulouse units

diff=(0.0316, -0.0870) = (523.4, -1439.6) toulouse units

peak level is 37.7dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 50: od080903: x cross section at y= 2.1143

Plot of od080903

file date: 2008 Sep 0 14h09

Toulouse Beam Tests at 488.6GHz

2000 September 8

Mercury Lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.3001arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2978arc mins

ellipticity=0.054

peak at x= 2.3573arc mins

ref at x= 2.3257arc mins

diff = 0.0316arc mins

peak level is 37.7dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 51: od080903: y cross section at x= 2.1143

Plot of od080903

file date: 2008 Sep 0 14h09

Toulouse Beam Tests at 488.6GHz

2000 September 8

Mercury Lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.2317arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2296arc mins

ellipticity=0.054

peak at y= 2.2388arc mins

ref at y= 2.3257arc mins

diff = -0.0870arc mins

peak level is 37.7dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 52: od080903: 3d mesh plot

Plot of od080903

file date: 2008 Sep 0 14h09

Toulouse Beam Tests at 488.6GHz

2000 September 8

Mercury Lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.2659arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.2637arc mins

ellipticity=0.054

peak=(2.3573, 2.2388)

ref pos=(2.3257, 2.3257)

diff=(0.0316, -0.0870)

peak level is 37.7dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 53: od080905: plotted peak level: 35.0000dBm, spacing: 1.00dBm

Plot of od080905

file date: 2008 Sep 0 9h39

Toulouse Beam Tests at 541.06GHz

2000 September 8

Mercury Lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.0868arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0849arc mins

ellipticity=0.077

peak=(2.4803, 2.3252) = (41059.7, 38491.3) toulouse units

ref pos=(2.3257, 2.3257) = (38500.0, 38500.0) toulouse units

diff=(0.1546, -0.0005) = (2559.7, -8.7) toulouse units

peak level is 35.1dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 54: od080905: x cross section at y= 2.5372

Plot of od080905
file date: 2008 Sep 0 9h39
Toulouse Beam Tests at 541.06GHz
2000 September 8

Mercury Lamp

Fit at 3.0dB
W3dB= 1.1289arc mins
W 3.0dB= 1.1269arc mins
ellipticity=0.077
peak at x= 2.4803arc mins
ref at x= 2.3257arc mins
diff = 0.1546arc mins
peak level is 34.9dBm
no correction for noise level

FIGURE 55: od080905: y cross section at x= 2.5372

Plot of od080905

file date: 2008 Sep 0 9h39

Toulouse Beam Tests at 541.06GHz

2000 September 8

Mercury Lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.0447arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0429arc mins

ellipticity=0.077

peak at y= 2.3252arc mins

ref at y= 2.3257arc mins

diff = -0.0005arc mins

peak level is 35.3dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 56: od080905: 3d mesh plot

Plot of od080905

file date: 2008 Sep 0 9h39

Toulouse Beam Tests at 541.06GHz

2000 September 8

Mercury Lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.0868arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0849arc mins

ellipticity=0.077

peak=(2.4803, 2.3252)

ref pos=(2.3257, 2.3257)

diff=(0.1546, -0.0005)

peak level is 35.1dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 57: od080904: plotted peak level: 34.0000dBm, spacing: 1.00dBm

Plot of od080904

file date: 2008 Sep 0 14h27

Toulouse Beam Tests at 578GHz

2000 September 8

Mercury Lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.0379arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0361arc mins

ellipticity=0.033

peak=(2.7233, 2.0650) = (45081.9, 34184.3) toulouse units

ref pos=(2.3257, 2.3257) = (38500.0, 38500.0) toulouse units

diff=(0.3976, -0.2607) = (6581.9, -4315.7) toulouse units

peak level is 34.1dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 58: od080904: x cross section at y= 2.1143

Plot of od080904

file date: 2008 Sep 0 14h27

Toulouse Beam Tests at 578GHz

2000 September 8

Mercury Lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.0552arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0534arc mins

ellipticity=0.033

peak at x= 2.7233arc mins

ref at x= 2.3257arc mins

diff = 0.3976arc mins

peak level is 34.1dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 59: od080904: y cross section at x= 2.5372

Plot of od080904

file date: 2008 Sep 0 14h27

Toulouse Beam Tests at 578GHz

2000 September 8

Mercury Lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.0205arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0188arc mins

ellipticity=0.033

peak at y= 2.0650arc mins

ref at y= 2.3257arc mins

diff = -0.2607arc mins

peak level is 34.2dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 60: od080904: 3d mesh plot

Plot of od080904

file date: 2008 Sep 0 14h27

Toulouse Beam Tests at 578GHz

2000 September 8

Mercury Lamp

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.0379arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0361arc mins

ellipticity=0.033

peak=(2.7233, 2.0650)

ref pos=(2.3257, 2.3257)

diff=(0.3976, -0.2607)

peak level is 34.1dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 61: beam alignment measurements at Toulouse using the Mercury Lamp (second set 2000-Sep-8)

- 495GHZ: □D080903.lob
- 549GHZ: □D080905.lob
- 572GHZ: □D080904.lob

Heating the Primary Reflector: A measurement was done at 572GHz using the spare Local Oscillator to illuminate the collimator. Beam measurements were taken with the telescope in ambient conditions. These are shown in Figures 62 to 65. The data is taken from file OD070902.lob. After several hours of heating, the primary reflector reached a temperature of 35C (??), with no temperature gradient across the reflector. Beam measurements done with the heated telescope are shown in Figures 66 to 69, plotted from data in file OD070903.lob.

For comparison, the two data sets were subtracted from one another and plotted in Figures 70 to 73. There is very little change in the beam profile before and after heating the telescope. The maximum deviation is a difference of ~3dB near the map edge, where reflection effects dominate. Within the main lobe, the difference between before and after is within 1dB. It is especially stable in the vertical direction.

FIGURE 62: od070902: plotted peak level: 39.0000dBm, spacing: 1.00dBm

Plot of od070902
file date: 2008 Sep 0 14h09
Toulouse Beam Tests at 572.6GHz
2000 September 7

source is the LO
This is BEFORE heating the telescope

Fit at 3.0dB
W3dB= 1.1078arc mins
W 3.0dB= 1.1059arc mins
ellipticity=0.023
peak=(2.4960, 2.2953) = (41318.3, 37996.7) toulouse units
ref pos=(2.3257, 2.3257) = (38500.0, 38500.0) toulouse units
diff=(0.1702, -0.0304) = (2818.3, -503.3) toulouse units
peak level is 40.0dBm
no correction for noise level

FIGURE 63: od070902: x cross section at y= 2.1143

Plot of od070902

file date: 2008 Sep 0 14h09

Toulouse Beam Tests at 572.6GHz

2000 September 7

source is the LO

This is BEFORE heating the telescope

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.0953arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0934arc mins

ellipticity=0.023

peak at x= 2.4960arc mins

ref at x= 2.3257arc mins

diff = 0.1702arc mins

peak level is 40.0dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 64: od070902: y cross section at x= 2.5372

Plot of od070902

file date: 2008 Sep 0 14h09

Toulouse Beam Tests at 572.6GHz

2000 September 7

source is the LO

This is BEFORE heating the telescope

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.1203arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.1184arc mins

ellipticity=0.023

peak at y= 2.2953arc mins

ref at y= 2.3257arc mins

diff = -0.0304arc mins

peak level is 40.1dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 65: od070902: 3d mesh plot

Plot of od070902

file date: 2008 Sep 0 14h09

Toulouse Beam Tests at 572.6GHz

2000 September 7

source is the LO

This is BEFORE heating the telescope

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.1078arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.1059arc mins

ellipticity=0.023

peak=(2.4960, 2.2953)

ref pos=(2.3257, 2.3257)

diff=(0.1702, -0.0304)

peak level is 40.0dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 66: od070903: plotted peak level: 38.0000dBm, spacing: 1.00dBm

Plot of od070903

file date: 2008 Sep 0 14h10

Toulouse Beam Tests at 572.6GHz

2000 September 7

source is the LO

this is AFTER heating the telescope

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.0899arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0880arc mins

ellipticity=0.014

peak=(2.5463, 2.3184) = (42152.2, 38378.9) toulouse units

ref pos=(2.5372, 2.5372) = (42000.0, 42000.0) toulouse units

diff=(0.0092, -0.2187) = (152.2, -3621.1) toulouse units

peak level is 38.8dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 67: od070903: x cross section at y= 2.1143

Plot of od070903

file date: 2008 Sep 0 14h10

Toulouse Beam Tests at 572.6GHz

2000 September 7

source is the LO

this is AFTER heating the telescope

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.0820arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0801arc mins

ellipticity=0.014

peak at x= 2.5463arc mins

ref at x= 2.5372arc mins

diff = 0.0092arc mins

peak level is 38.8dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 68: od070903: y cross section at x= 2.5372

Plot of od070903

file date: 2008 Sep 0 14h10

Toulouse Beam Tests at 572.6GHz

2000 September 7

source is the LO

this is AFTER heating the telescope

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.0977arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0958arc mins

ellipticity=0.014

peak at y= 2.3184arc mins

ref at y= 2.5372arc mins

diff = -0.2187arc mins

peak level is 38.9dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 69: od070903: 3d mesh plot

Plot of od070903

file date: 2008 Sep 0 14h10

Toulouse Beam Tests at 572.6GHz

2000 September 7

source is the LO

this is AFTER heating the telescope

Fit at 3.0dB

W3dB= 1.0899arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0880arc mins

ellipticity=0.014

peak=(2.5463, 2.3184)

ref pos=(2.5372, 2.5372)

diff=(0.0092, -0.2187)

peak level is 38.8dBm

no correction for noise level

FIGURE 70: od070903: plotted peak level: 2.0000dBm, spacing: 0.10dBm

2000 September 8/9

relative difference between BEFORE and AFTER heating the telescope
Toulouse CESR Beam test at 572.6GHz

Source is the spare LO

this plot is normalised to have zero difference at the beam centre
which allows for some offset in absolute level between the two measurements
maximum difference is 4dB at the edge (probably due to reflections)
main lobe difference is relatively flat

except for larger variations at the corners, all differences are within 1dB

W3dB= 1.0899arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0880arc mins

peak=(2.5463, 2.3184) = (42152.2, 38378.9) toulouse units

ref pos=(2.5372, 2.5372) = (42000.0, 42000.0) toulouse units

diff=(0.0092, -0.2187) = (152.2, -3621.1) toulouse units

peak level is 3.6dBm

FIGURE 71: od070903: x cross section at y= 2.1143

x (arc mins)

2000 September 8/9

relative difference between BEFORE and AFTER heating the telescope

Toulouse CESR Beam test at 572.6GHz

Source is the spare LO

this plot is normalised to have zero difference at the beam centre

which allows for some offset in absolute level between the two measurements

maximum difference is 4dB at the edge (probably due to reflections)

main lobe difference is relatively flat

except for larger variations at the corners, all differences are within 1dB

W3dB= 1.0820arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0801arc mins

peak at x= 2.5463arc mins

ref at x= 2.5372arc mins

diff = 0.0092arc mins

peak level is 3.6dBm

FIGURE 72: od070903: y cross section at x= 2.5372

2000 September 8/9

relative difference between BEFORE and AFTER heating the telescope

Toulouse CESR Beam test at 572.6GHz

Source is the spare LO

this plot is normalised to have zero difference at the beam centre

which allows for some offset in absolute level between the two measurements

maximum difference is 4dB at the edge (probably due to reflections)

main lobe difference is relatively flat

except for larger variations at the corners, all differences are within 1dB

W3dB= 1.0977arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0958arc mins

peak at y= 2.3184arc mins

ref at y= 2.5372arc mins

diff = -0.2187arc mins

peak level is 3.6dBm

FIGURE 73: od070903: 3d mesh plot

2000 September 8/9

relative difference between BEFORE and AFTER heating the telescope
Toulouse CESR Beam test at 572.6GHz

Source is the spare LO

this plot is normalised to have zero difference at the beam centre

which allows for some offset in absolute level between the two measurements

maximum difference is 4dB at the edge (probably due to reflections)

main lobe difference is relatively flat

except for larger variations at the corners, all differences are within 1dB

W3dB= 1.0899arc mins

W 3.0dB= 1.0880arc mins

peak=(2.5463, 2.3184)

ref pos=(2.5372, 2.5372)

diff=(0.0092, -0.2187)

peak level is 3.6dBm